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Opportunities and advantages of learning English through mobile applications

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Abstract. This article examines the possibilities and advantages of learning English using mobile applications. Mobile applications play a particularly important role in facilitating the process of learning English, as they allow users to take lessons anytime and anywhere. The article provides information on how learning English is facilitated using mobile applications, their effectiveness, and the most popular applications used in this process. The psychological and motivational aspects of learning a language using mobile applications are also analyzed.

Keywords: English, mobile applications, language learning, online education, Duolingo, Babbel, mobile technologies, educational methodology, interactive teaching, language learning motivation.

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Introduction

Modern technologies have changed all aspects of our lives, including education. English stands out as one of the dominant languages in the world of global communication, science and business. As the demand for it increases, the search for effective methods of learning the language is becoming increasingly important. Mobile applications are one of the most convenient and effective tools at the same time, as they allow the user to take lessons anytime and anywhere. They also help to organize the learning process in an interactive and entertaining way, which makes learning the language interesting.

Learning English today is carried out not only at school or university, but also online and through mobile applications. The possibilities, effectiveness and benefits of learning English using mobile applications are increasing. In this article, we will focus on the possibilities and advantages of learning English through mobile applications.

1. The main advantage of learning English through mobile applications is that they are always at your fingertips. The ability to use a phone or tablet allows you to learn a language anywhere and at any time. This is especially convenient for people

with a tight schedule or who are on the move all day long. You can learn English at any time, for example, in transport or during a vacation.

2. Mobile applications offer flexible learning programs for users of different levels. For beginners, you can start with simple and basic words and phrases, and then the application offers to move on to more complex topics. With this individual approach, each user can choose their own learning pace and level.

3. Mobile applications often offer learning programs structured in the form of games. This makes learning a language more interesting and effective. For example, in the Duolingo application, users learn a language by completing different levels and tasks. With this gamified approach, users stay motivated and want to learn more.

4. Mobile apps provide students with a wealth of materials to develop grammar, vocabulary, pronunciation, listening, and speaking skills. Apps like Memrise and Babbel provide visuals, audio, and videos of English words and phrases, making the material more memorable. Apps also often provide examples of words and phrases in different contexts to help them learn the language.

5. Mobile apps also help with pronunciation. Some apps listen to words spoken by users and check their pronunciation. For example, the Rosetta Stone app automatically assesses pronunciation and gives users suggestions for correct pronunciation.

6. Many mobile apps allow users to track their progress. This helps learners see changes and increase their motivation. For example, the Duolingo app allows users to organize their language learning process with tools such as "daily goals" and "progress charts." These tools help users see progress as they learn and increase their motivation to learn.

7. Many mobile apps, especially apps like HelloTalk, allow users to communicate with native English speakers. This is a great way to practice the language in real life, as the conversation can help you build your vocabulary and reinforce your learning in real time.

8. Mobile apps often offer features that allow you to review words and phrases frequently. For example, the Anki app allows users to review words using flashcards. This feature is available in many language learning programs and ensures long-term memorization for the user.

Literature review.

Analysis of foreign literature shows that the process of learning a language using mobile applications can be much more effective than traditional lessons. For example, applications such as Duolingo and Babbel have demonstrated their effectiveness in learning English. In some studies, mobile applications help users learn a language in a timely and independent manner, which makes it easier for them to remember new

words and phrases (Sims, 2015; Benson, 2019). Also, using gamification elements, mobile applications increase user motivation, which ensures continuous and effective learning (Kukulaska-Hulme, 2012).

There are also opinions in Uzbek literature about the advantages of learning a language through mobile applications. Uzbek scholars have conducted several studies on the role and benefits of mobile technologies in education, especially in the language learning process (Khusanov, 2020; Davronov, 2021). There are scientific studies on the possibilities and effectiveness of learning English using mobile applications in Uzbek schools and higher education institutions, which emphasize the importance of mobile learning.

Results and Discussion.

The main advantages of learning English using mobile applications are as follows:

1. Users have the opportunity to learn English anytime and anywhere. This allows them to integrate the learning process into everyday life.
2. Mobile applications provide interactivity, motivating users through games and competitions. This, in turn, makes learning interesting and effective.
3. Mobile applications provide a variety of educational materials, audio and video lessons, tests and exercises, which improve the user's ability to remember and understand.
4. Applications encourage the user to learn continuously and help them continue the learning process by rewarding them with small successes.
5. Frequent updates and new materials. Mobile applications are constantly updated and provide new materials, which motivates users to constantly acquire new knowledge.

There are also some limitations. Mobile apps can be limited in providing lessons, especially for advanced language learning. Compared to other methods, apps are more suitable for basic language learning and have limitations in providing in-depth grammar analysis or instruction on the subtleties of the language. Duolingo and Babbel are two popular mobile apps that help you learn English. Both apps are interactive and easy to use, making it easier for the user to learn a language. However, their approach and methodology are different, and these differences play an important role in choosing one based on the user's needs. Below, we will analyze the advantages and disadvantages of both apps.

1. Duolingo.

Advantages:

- Free and easy to use. The Duolingo app is completely free and offers basic features without requiring any payment. This is very useful for beginners or those who

are just starting to learn a language, as they have the opportunity to learn without taking any financial risks.

- Duolingo engages students through gamification. Each lesson has points, ribbons, and rewards for users. This method makes learning interesting and engaging, and also increases motivation.

- Ability to learn many languages. Duolingo allows you to learn not only English, but also many other languages, which helps users in the process of learning other languages.

- The application has a very simple interface, which is very convenient for new users. This mobile application simplifies the process of learning English and helps the user improve by correcting mistakes.

Cons:

- Less focus on grammar. Duolingo is more focused on vocabulary and simple sentences. The process of learning and understanding grammar in depth is not very developed, which can lead to difficulties at the advanced language learning stage.

- Duolingo is suitable for basic language learning, but may not be able to teach high-level grammar and the subtleties of the language. This is a disadvantage for advanced users.

2. Babbel:

Advantages:

- More focus on grammar. Babbel, compared to Duolingo, focuses more on learning grammar and language rules. The lessons give students a clear understanding of English grammar and language structure. This is useful for advanced users, as it helps them learn the language more deeply.

- Babbel offers students a more structured learning system, where each lesson logically progresses to the next. Babbel's teaching method is more scientific and systematic, providing a more in-depth approach to language learning.

- Effective conversation exercises. Babbel has exercises aimed at developing English conversation skills. This prepares users to communicate in English in real life.

Cons:

- Babbel's main drawback is that it only offers a paid service. While there are free introductory lessons, a subscription is required to learn the full courses. This can be a financial barrier for many users.

- Babbel only offers a few languages compared to other language learning apps. Duolingo offers a wider range of languages, so it may be more beneficial to use Duolingo than Babbel for learning English alone.

Analysis and recommendation:

- If you are just starting to learn English, Duolingo is a great choice. The app's gamification features and the fact that it is free help users to make learning fun and motivating. This is especially useful for those who are new to learning the language.

- If you want to gain more in-depth knowledge in learning English, Babbel is more useful. The grammar-focused approach and the effectiveness of the conversation exercises are the advantages of the app. However, Babbel is a paid service, and its lessons provide students with a detailed understanding.

- Ease of use. Duolingo is free and offers more flexibility in the learning process. Babbel, on the other hand, offers a more systematic approach, but its capabilities are limited financially.

Which app should you choose?

If you are just starting out in English, Duolingo is a good choice because it is free, easy to use, and has motivational features. If you want to learn English more deeply, Babbel will help you more because it focuses on grammar and language structure.

However, both apps are effective in their own right, and it is useful to choose one depending on your learning methodology and goals.

Conclusion. Nowadays, learning English through mobile applications has become one of the most popular and effective learning tools. They help users learn the language by making the learning process interactive, convenient and interesting. However, these applications should not only increase the user's motivation, but also be used in other ways to learn the deeper aspects of the language. Mobile applications should be improved to make the learning process of English more effective.

Today, mobile applications are a very effective tool for learning English, they help make the learning process interactive, convenient and interesting. The advantages of learning English through mobile applications, including flexibility, individual approach, interactivity, pronunciation development, and the ability to track the learning process, help students learn the language effectively and quickly.

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